

Title: Chemistry in everyday Life for NEET and JEE students in One Page

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Abstract

Chemistry is particularly important in everyday life since it affects health, cleanliness, nutrition, and industrial operations. This review examines the utilization of chemistry in medications, food additives, and cleaning agents, emphasizing drug action mechanisms, chemical classifications, and practical advantages. It talks about the chemical makeup of soaps, detergents, and food preservatives, as well as how important pharmaceuticals like antacids, antihistamines, and tranquilizers are for health. The report also talks about mind mapping as a way to comprehend how molecular science relates to everyday life.

Key Words

Chemistry in everyday life, Drugs, Antacids, Detergents, Food additives, Artificial sweeteners, Mind mapping

CHEMISTRY IN EVERYDAY LIFE

BASED ON PHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECT

This classification provides range of drugs available for a particular type of problem.

CLASSIFICATION OF DRUGS

BASED ON CHEMICAL STRUCTURE

Drugs having common structural features are grouped together in one class.

BASED ON MOLECULAR TARGET

Based on the interaction with biomolecules such as lipids, proteins, carbohydrates & nucleic acids.

FOOD ENHANCING

- **ARTIFICIAL SWEETENING AGENTS:** Natural Sweeteners (sucrose) and artificial sweeteners (aspartame) that sweeten the food.
- **FOOD PRESERVATIVES:** Prevent spoilage of food due to microbial growth. (Table salt, sugar)

BASED ON DRUG ACTION

It is based on drug's effect on a certain biochemical process.

CLEANING SOAPS

SOAPS

Sodium or potassium salts of long chain of fatty acids like stearic acid, and oleic.

TYPES OF SOAPS

- Toilet Soaps
- Floating Soaps
- Medicated Soaps
- Shower chips
- Transparent Soaps
- Laundry Soaps

SYNTHETIC DETERGENTS

Sodium salts of alkyl benzene sulphonic acids

- Three types of detergents:
- Anionic detergents
 - Cationic detergents
 - Non ionic detergents

CLEANSING ACTION OF DETERGENTS

The cleansing action of detergents are some as that of soaps.

ANTACIDS

Substances that neutralize the excess acid & raise pH in stomach.
Ex: Ranitidine

ANTIHISTAMINES

Drugs which diminish the main action of histamine. (lead to allergic reactions) These are also known as anti-allergic drugs.
Ex: Brompheniramine

THERAPEUTIC ACTION OF DRUGS

NEUROLOGICALLY ACTIVE DRUGS

Tranquilizers: Chemicals used for treatment of stress & in mild or even severe mental diseases.
Ex: Iproniazid

Analgesics: Reduce pain without causing impairment of consciousness, mental confusion or paralysis of nervous system.

CLASSIFIED IN TWO TYPES:

- Non-narcotic (Non-addictive)—Aspirin
- Narcotic—Morphine

ANTIFERTILITY DRUGS

Birth control pills (Norethindrone)

CHEMICALS IN FOOD

Synthetic or natural chemical substances added to food preparation for different purposes are known as food additives.

PURPOSE

- For food preservation
- Enhancing their appeal
- Adding nutritive value

ANTIMICROBIALS

(a) **Antibiotics:** It is used to treat infection because of their low toxicity for humans & animals.
Ex: Penicillin

(b) **Antiseptics & Disinfectants:** Chemicals which either inhibit or prevent the growth of micro-organism. Antiseptics are applied to living tissues whereas disinfectants are applied to inanimate objects.

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